

Statistical Significance of $d/dx \ln(W)$ where W =the Quantum Bound Wavefunction

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In (1), the bound Schrodinger equation is written in terms of a velocity field: $v = \hbar/m dW/dx / W$ (where W , the wavefunction is real) leading to: $-\hbar^2/2m \text{grad dot } v - m/2 v \text{ dot } v + V(x) = E$. Here we note that $\ln(\text{probability})$ is information in information sciences and try to consider why $\ln(W)$ should be associated with information and secondly why d/dx appears.

Newtonian Mechanics

Newton's second law $dp/dt = \text{Force}$ and $.5mv(x)v(x) + V(x) = E$ show that the dynamic variable $v(x)$, speed, is governed by forces, (i.e. by Force or $V(x)$). Force or $V(x)$, however, affects the variable momentum ($mv(x)$ nonrelativistic) or energy $.5 mv(x)v(x)$ (nonrelativistic). In other words, the variables associated with interactions which govern speed, contain speed itself.

A second point we wish to consider is the definition of $v(x) = dx/dt$. Experimentally, one would require a finite dx and a finite dt and so arguing that dx and dt can approach 0 is mathematically convenient, but may be physically problematic to achieve. Furthermore, the particle accelerates in Newtonian physics and so it is not clear how one is measuring its velocity at the same time it interacts and accelerates. If the acceleration is small and dx and dt very tiny, then $v(x)$ measured = $v(x) + dv(x)$, so one has an estimate of the speed.

Information Science

In information science, $\ln(\text{probability}) = \text{information}$, but we ask: To what does this information pertain? In the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution;

$$\ln(\exp(-e_i/T)) = -e_i/T \quad \text{where } p(x) = \exp(-e_i/T) \text{ is unnormalized} \quad ((1))$$

It seems that there is a total energy of E which is distributed among N particles and T is a statistical parameter characterizing the equilibrium and linked to total energy for an ideal gas. If one were to take:

$$d/de \ln(p(e_i)) = -1/T \quad ((2)) \quad \text{then one would obtain information about the statistical parameter alone.}$$

Thus, the full information $\ln(p(e_i))$ yields the distribution variable divided by a characteristic statistical parameter and a derivative may pick out one or the other. We try to apply these ideas to the quantum mechanical case.

Quantum Free Particle

The wavefunction of a quantum free particle is $\exp(ipx)$ (one dimension). If one considers this to be an unnormalized probability, then according to information science:

$$\ln(\exp(ipx)) = ipx \quad ((3))$$

Here one sees that x is the distribution variable and p plays the role of the statistical parameter. The complex i shows that one has periodicity. Thus, $\exp(ipx)$ is associated with motion in space, in particular with the breaking of space into units of \hbar/p . Thus:

$$\text{Wavelength} = \hbar/p \quad ((4)) \text{ is the statistical parameter}$$

As in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, one may take d/dx to pull out p which is linked with the statistical parameter, but why should one do this? We argue that not only is p linked with a statistical parameter ($\exp(ipx)$ suggests uniform motion in a cycle of px), but it is a dynamical variable linked with impulses in Newtonian mechanics. In the case of Newtonian mechanics, one has determinism, i.e. a knowledge of $p(x)$ and $v(x)$ in each tiny dx , but now p values are statistical parameters and instead of having one, like T temperature, in the Maxwell-Boltzmann ideal gas, one could have many p (momenta).

We first note that:

$$\exp(ipx) \rightarrow d/dx \ln(\exp(ipx)) = p \quad \text{and in the nonrelativistic case } p=mv \quad ((4))$$

At the same time, $v=\text{constant}$. One might argue that for a free particle which does not interact, there is no need to use $d/dx \ln(p)$. Simply writing $v=\text{constant}$ is enough. ((4)), however, shows the role of p as a statistical parameter in a repeating distribution in x with \hbar/p cycle lengths. The breaking of space into \hbar/p units is critical physically because it means that one has probabilistic interactions in the \hbar/p length instead of the deterministic Newtonian ones. Thus, $\exp(ipx)$ should be used in a description of interactions in the quantum case.

Quantum Bound State

If one begins with the Newtonian conservation of energy equation:

$$p^2/2m + V(x) = E \quad ((5))$$

one might ask: What changes in the quantum case? We have argued that even in the case of a single constant p , $\exp(ipx)$, one has a probabilistic scenario, i.e. a one parameter distribution. If various p values may be stirred up, then one has many distributions $\exp(ipx)$, $\exp(ip_1x)$, $\exp(ip_2x)$ etc. Given that p is the quantity of interest in ((5)), one might consider an average of p , i.e.

$$KE(x) = \left\{ \sum \text{over } p \quad p^2/2m \ a(p) \ \exp(ipx) \right\} / \left\{ \sum \text{over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx) \right\} \quad ((6))$$

In ((6)), one does not see the appearances of: $d/dx \ln(W)$, where $W = \sum \text{over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx)$ and this is fine as ((6)) in ((5)) is equivalent to the Schrodinger equation. The equation is stochastic because of the averaging over p values.

This then leads to the result of (1). In (1), the authors decide to write the bound Schrodinger equation in terms of a velocity field;

$$v = \hbar/m \, dW/dx \quad (W = \text{real for the bound case}) \quad ((7))$$

Then the identity:

$$d/dx (dW/dx / W) = d/dx (dW/dx) / W - dW/dx \, dW/dx / (WW) \quad ((8))$$

allows one to rewrite the Schrodinger equation as:

$$-\hbar^2/2m \, \text{grad dot } v - m/2 \, v \cdot v + V(x) = E \quad ((9))$$

We ask: Why does one wish to write the Schrodinger equation in terms of a velocity field? We suggest that perhaps it is to demonstrate the presence of information (from information science) in the bound quantum mechanical problem.

We have noted above that $\exp(ipx)$ is a probability and that $d/dx \ln(\exp(ipx)) = ip$. Then:

Sum over p $a(p) \exp(ipx) = W$ is also a probability, i.e. a weighted one with different statistical parameters p . ((10)).

Thus, $d/dx \ln(W)$ should have an interpretation in terms of information science. It is in fact the average of p , i.e. the average of the different statistical parameters.

$d/dx \ln(W)$ is a relevant statistical term. It is also linked to what should be a relevant physical term because a priori if $\langle pp \rangle$ is significant because it appears in ((6), $\langle p \rangle$ should also be relevant. In fact, given the identity ((8)), one may link the two and rewrite the Schrodinger equation in terms of a relevant d/dx information from information science, i.e. ((9)).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that $\ln(\text{probability}) = \text{information in information science}$. We further note that in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, this implies $\ln(\exp(-e_i/T)) = -e_i/T$, for an unnormalized probability. Here e_i is the distribution variable and T , temperature, a statistical parameter. Taking d/de_i selects the statistical parameter. We argue that a very similar situation occurs for a quantum free particle wavefunction (probability) $\exp(ipx)$ unnormalized, i.e. $\ln(\exp(ipx)) = ipx$. Here x is the distribution variable, but it shows that there is cycling over \hbar/p units, and this is the statistical parameter. It turns out that this statistical parameter is related to p , momentum, which is linked with interaction (impulse). Thus, there is a combination of a probability and information from information science and an impulse parameter p .

If one writes the Newtonian conservation of energy equation; $pp/2m + V(x) = E$, one might write pp as an average: $\{\text{Sum over } p \, a(p) \, pp/2m \, \exp(ipx)\} / W(x)$. This, however, does not show the information science information. The relation ((8)), however, links $\langle pp \rangle$ to $d/dx \ln(W)$

which is not only related to information science and statistics, but also yields $\langle p \rangle$ which is physically relevant for an interaction, we argue. This, we argue, is why the Schrodinger equation, written in terms of $\langle p \rangle$ (as in (1)), may display both physical and information science features.

References

1. Lynd, N. Computational Stochastic Mechanics of a Simple Bound State (April 2025)
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